

Possibilities for mathematics education in a university-school partnership

Raquel Milani, University of Sao Paulo, ✉ rmilani@usp.br

Patricia R. Linardi, Federal University of Sao Paulo

Michela Tuchapesk da Silva, University of Sao Paulo

This ongoing project is about initial and continuing teacher education of science and mathematics, more precisely at the university-school interface. In this perspective, the relationship with the school which participates in the project, as well as the development of research, emerge from the processes of action research. In this text, we present the actions we have developed about mathematics education with all the participants of the project. Teachers and educators problematized ideas from an investigative activity on numbers, based on landscapes of investigation (Skovsmose). From this, the participants start to criticize the didactic textbook used in the school, as mandatory, contributing to their critical development teaching professional. The way the participants have faced teaching during COVID-19 pandemic is also discussed.

The research project

The present project is located in the field of research on initial and continuing education of science and mathematics teachers, more precisely at the university and school interface. Both institutions are interrelated in search of improving the quality of teaching and, for consequently, the professional development of teachers, teacher educators and managers involved, and the quality of learning of undergraduate students in science and mathematics, and students from the participating school. The project is financed by a Brazilian development agency (Grant #2018/16585-1, Sao Paulo Research Foundation – FAPESP).

The relationship with the school, as well as the development of research that are part of the project, emerged as a movement, an action research process (Thiollent, 2004), in which the school, the teachers and the management group appeared simultaneously as subjects and objects of investigation. Researchers from two Brazilian public universities, management participants and teachers from a public school in the State of Sao Paulo meet periodically in forums constituted at the school and at universities. In this process, the motives of the various participants, as well as the objectives of the group's collective work, have been refined and articulated in the direction of building the partnership developed in this project.

More specifically, we seek to discuss possible answers to the following questions: “Which changes in teaching, in school management and in the teacher education of prospective

Please cite as: Milani, R., Linardi, P. R., & Tuchapesk, M. (2021). Possibilities for mathematics education in a university-school partnership. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 197–202). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5392363>

teachers and school teachers are being leveraged by the work developed in the collaborative partnership? What elements enhance such changes?”.

The current group of researchers is made up of a very heterogeneous group, whether in their graduation and PhD (pedagogy, philosophy, specialists in teaching and training teachers in the areas of science and mathematics, and specialist in educational public policies), or in their professional experiences and school levels practices.

According to Foerste (2004), the partnerships between universities and schools can assume different objectives, levels of involvement and integration of participants. In this sense, Jones *et al* (2016) state that the types of partnerships are defined by three different levels of integration of the subjects: *connective partnerships* are those in which exchange relationships are established and each of the involved parties offers something to exchange with the partners; *generative partnerships* occur when subjects are able to help each other, through the development of collective projects, which leads to changes in the structure of existing activities; and *transformative partnerships* are those in which there is active and collaborative involvement of all participants in a reflexive-critical practice, guided by the articulation between theory and practice, in order to develop all participating members. It is through this last partnership that the project seeks to develop.

In this multiplicity, the relationship between university and elementary school is expressed in a heterogeneous and diversified way, generating networks in which acceptance/denial, rupture/continuity/discontinuity are threads whose intertwining produces interesting processes. Such processes “give meaning to partnership movements, teacher professional training and the insertion of research as a constituent of training, in which we have constituted ourselves as actors in the process” (Almeida et al., 2000, p. 53). In this sense, the authors point out that recognizing the various roles that the university and the school assume, modifying or producing them, is fundamental to identify the borders, the overlaps and the specific areas of work. According to the authors, the outcomes of these partnerships provide a “meaningful panorama of the teacher education, considering the teachers as critical producers of their pedagogical work” (Almeida et al., 2000, p. 53).

Based on Fiorentini (2009), Nacarato (2016) and Oliveira (2015), we established discussions regarding partnerships in mathematics education. The authors point out that the partnerships between the university and the school enable conditions for teachers and prospective teachers to reflect on trends in mathematics education, as well as to discuss the mathematics curriculum at school, in order to face the difficulties that often are raised in the teaching practice.

With such a perspective, we hope to bring contributions both to the improvement of the teaching at the partner school, as well as the learning of teaching, the professional teacher development and the respective areas of research in these fields. Thus, we understand the relationship between learning of teaching and professional development as processes that emerge from the needs created in their practice and from the internship activity. In this way, we hope that the actions shared between prospective teachers, school teachers and university professors can contribute to the dialogue between different types of knowledge.

In this present text, the focus is to present and the discuss one of the training actions developed in the project in order to contribute to the two research questions, related to the changes in the mathematics teaching and in the teacher education of the participants of the project, and to the elements developed in the collaborative partnership that leverage such changes.

Teacher education meetings on mathematics education

In 2019, we held action research meetings of the group. In monthly meetings, at the universities the researchers met for reflect on relevant topics related to the project's issues. After some of them, on inquiry-based science teaching, there were two meetings on mathematics education in the early years of elementary school. The theme was chosen and organized by the group. Critical Mathematics Education (Skovsmose, 2011) was the theoretical perspective chosen by the universities researchers to base the meeting. The school teachers intended to discuss students' difficulties in learning mathematics and to know different ways of teaching. The teacher educators' intentions were to understand how school teachers used to teach mathematics, and to learn from them about students' difficulties.

In order to achieve these aims, previously, for the first meeting, we requested that participants to read the text "Landscapes of Investigation", by Ole Skovsmose (2000). We have chosen that text for three reasons: 1 – the text is based on critical mathematics education and by adopting this theoretical framework to reflect on the mathematics teaching is a possibility to question what is given as true; 2 – the proposal presented in this text (the landscapes of investigation) departs from a well known context to the school teacher and close to their practice (the paradigm of exercise); 3 – the author presents the mathematics as a tool to interpret situations and make decisions, and argues that mathematical discoveries made by the students can enable different qualities of learning. We expected these ideas raise in the study meetings.

Thus, at that meeting, an investigative activity on numbers, proposed in this text, was developed. An investigative activity aims to enable students to make discoveries, to have an active participation in solving the activity and to be responsible for their learning process. Such discoveries do not concern genuine knowledge of mathematics, but rather new knowledge for those who carry out the action. Dialogue is the form of communication that predominates in this type of activity.

The work with the landscape of investigation was developed in small groups and encouraged participants to explore a table to discover some regularities and numerical patterns. It was possible to notice that the participants shared their findings, doubts and hypotheses with their colleagues. Each idea raised in the small groups was presented and discussed with everyone. Views were shared. The action of understanding what the other was saying was present, and this is an essential element both for dialogue in the learning process and for the development of teacher education.

Some investigative questions were raised regarding the patterns and regularities of the referred numeric table. Surprise, restlessness and suspicious smiles were expressed by the participants when carrying out the activity. The invitation to investigate had been accepted by the group. The curiosity to try to find out why there were certain patterns persisted throughout the meeting. We realized that the discussion about generalizations, so important in the algebra of the early years, was put into action, because, during the activity, legitimate mathematical knowledge was raised for that group and essential for the development of the proposed task.

We reflected on the similarity between the activity carried out and those developed in previous meetings on inquiry-based science teaching. Raising hypotheses, evaluating them, arguing, making discoveries, dialoguing with colleagues are some of the common actions that we perceived among the proposals discussed for the teaching of mathematics and science. These actions are also important elements which enables changes in the mathematics teaching in the early years.

The second meeting on mathematics education began resuming the investigative activity carried out at the previous meeting. We emphasize the importance of teachers provide moments to the school students make discoveries in mathematics classes, playing an active role in the activity developed. Important aspects of Skovsmose's text (2000) were raised and discussed by the participants. We noticed that there is a huge difference between investigative classes, such as the activity we developed, and those based on the paradigm of exercise, in which the teacher explains the content, shows some examples and the students reproduce, in a list of exercises, what they heard from the teacher.

Because of the investigative activity we run in the previous meeting involved generalizations, we also discussed about Algebra in the early years. The search for patterns in numerical and graphical sequences and in tables, such as the one we explored in that meeting, is an aspect of algebra that can be worked on in the early years.

The second part of this meeting was intended for the presentation, by the school teachers, of the didactic material "Mathematics Education for the Early Years" (EMAI), used in the state schools of Sao Paulo, pointing out what the material is and how it is used. It should be noted that the teachers had the opportunity to dedicate themselves, in a group, to read and discuss the material. In their presentation, the teachers verbalized that this reading allowed them to demystify how to use it. They realized that the material is proposed as a support and not as a manual to be used daily and in a tied way, as it was presented to them in many moments of continuing education, provided by the management team of state schools. In this way, the teachers started to characterize it as a collaborative project of continuing education among the teachers of each school. Outbursts, complaints and solutions were verbalized.

Subsequently, we analyzed the summary of the material to see how it was organized. We identified that the language of the EMAI is very imperative ("do", "distribute", "ask"), which restricts the possibilities for the teacher to decide how best to develop the activity proposed

in the material. We also discussed the pressure that the author of these types of text experiences when producing didactic material.

The group started to question the possibilities of making the use of the didactic material more flexible. In order to connect the discussion on landscapes of investigation and the didactic material, one of the professors have raised the following question: Is it possible to create “landscapes of investigation” (Skovsmose, 2000) from the guidelines prescribed by the material? A deeply awareness and knowledge about the didactic material was one of the conditions considered by the group to be essential in order to proceed with the search for an answer to this question. The meeting ended at this time and with such a proposal. Considering the discussions played at these meeting we understand we were moving towards promoting changes both in the teaching of mathematics and in the teacher education.

The discussions and reflections, made by the school teachers about their teaching and didactic material, were important to their education, and also to highlight elements for thinking about and developing university-school partnership actions. For example, we realize that, in the beginning of the research project, the school teachers understood collaboration in an objective way to help them in some difficulty, and not as the possibility of a joint work that would contribute to thinking together about the development of a certain subject or a different approach to discuss with students. Thus, the discussions and verbalizations of the teachers show us how the partnership has potentialized the school’s activities in relation to changes in the teaching.

The discussions were interrupted due to the end of the year and the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic. With regard to the specific issues of mathematics education, the year 2020 was intended for the collaboration between school teachers and educators in organizing the remote classes held with the few students who had technical, psychological and family conditions to follow on-line teaching. The classes in the State of Sao Paulo were held and made available by a media center, which did not count on the participation of the teachers themselves in its production. In this way, what was revealed was a loss of their didactic choices and, consequently, a challenge for the continuity of our project.

Thus, the two mathematics education meetings raised important questions regarding the professional development of the teachers. Throughout the year 2020, such meetings reverberated in their speech in the project remote meetings that followed and in the interviews provided by them. We intend, as one of the next steps of the project with regard to mathematics education, to return to the records related to these meetings (audios, interviews and written conversations on whatsApp), looking for elements that contribute to the potentiality of the collaborative partnership.

Finally, we understand that the project plays a political role, by offering, through the interaction between the participants, subsidies so that answers and solutions can be found in order to promote transformative actions in the professional development of all those involved.

References

- Almeida, C.M.C., Amorim, A. C. R., Pacheco, D., Silva, L. L. M., Galzerani, M. C. B., Bagnato, M. H. S., Ferreira, N. S. A. F., & Scorsi, R. A. (2000). Professores da universidade e da escola básica: Parceiros no ensino e na pesquisa. *Pro-posições*, 1(4), 43–55.
- Fiorentini, D. (2009). Educação matemática: Diálogos entre universidade e escola. *Anais do Encontro Gaúcho de Educação Matemática*, http://www.projetos.unijui.edu.br/matematica/cd_egem/fscommand/CO/CO1.pdf
- Foerste, E. (2004). Parceria na formação de professores. *Revista Iberoamericana de Educación*, 34(3), 1–12.
- Jones, M., Hobbs, L., Kenny, J., Campbell, C., Chittleborough, G., Gilbert, A., Herbert, S., & Redman, C. (2016). Successful university-school partnerships: An interpretive framework to inform partnership practice. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 60, 108–120.
- Nacarato, A. M. (2016). A parceria universidade-escola: Utopia ou possibilidade de formação continuada no âmbito das políticas públicas? *Revista Brasileira de Educação*, 21(66), 699–716.
- Oliveira, N. Z. M. (2015). *Parceria entre universidade e escola em projetos de educação matemática* [Doctoral dissertation, Universidade Estadual Paulista].
- Skovsmose, O. (2011). *An invitation to critical mathematics education*. Sense Publishers.
- Skovsmose, O. (2000). Cenários para investigação. *Bolema: Boletim de Educação Matemática*, 13(14), 66–91.
- Thiollent, M. (2004). *Metodologia da pesquisa-ação*. São Paulo: Cortez.